

“Emerging Marketing Trends & Analysis of Consumer Satisfaction towards Food-Ordering Apps with reference to Zomato”

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ABSTRACT

The rapid growth of online food delivery services has increased very traditionally in the replacement of offline restaurants. This study revealed about youngsters are coming up with innovative concepts to counterpart untouched concerned area of consumers, which is being an important reason for the success of a business nowadays. The objective of the study which shows customer satisfaction & being an awareness of ordering food through various apps. This research paper has many aspects of online food sites. Different services are given by application that makes consumers happy & satisfied. The research concluded that customer who lives in the rural area is also satisfied by using the online food ordering website is bright, facilities, comfort, user-friendliness are the key feature of online website success.

This study delves into the emerging marketing trends within the food-tech landscape, with a focus on the renowned platform, Zomato. In an era marked by rapid technological advancements and shifting consumer preferences, the food industry has undergone significant transformations. Zomato, as a pioneering player in the food-tech domain, offers a compelling case study to explore the dynamic marketing strategies shaping the sector.

Key words: Marketing Trends, Emerging, Food Industry, Marketing Strategies, Artificial Intelligence, counterpart, customer satisfaction, food ordering app, user-friendliness.

Introduction

Food and water are the sources of energy of human beings. Food gives us the energy to have a balanced health and protect us from diseases. So, food acts as a major role in the life of human beings. Those days' people used to cook healthy foods and serve their families (Tsang et al., 2004). After few decades people started moving to restaurants or hotels to have their food. In this modern technology, the usage of android applications has increased quickly in recent years. Online ordering systems are maintaining a good relationship with the customers, which is being an important reason for the success of a business (Wan et al., 2008). The online food ordering method is increasing in the Indian market day by day. There are many apps which have been founded for ordering our foods peoples are also very active in using the apps for ordering the foods (Boyer & Hult, 2005). As there are more advantages in these apps the customers find it as a convenient form of ordering food online (De Korte & Van Lingen, 2006).

The main advantages of online food apps are:

- Ordering through mobile.
- It is fast, easy, and comfortable for customers.
- No misunderstanding between the customers and suppliers of foods.

- Food ordering is opened 24/7.

Statement of problem

Nowadays people are starting to move from traditional food distribution to online food delivery (Anckar & D'inciau, 2002). If the online food supply industry is fully well developed in upcoming years, it may be the greatest competence in the traditional food supply industry. In such a case, there is an opportunity to study the changes that have occurred in the restaurants' services through the implementation of the new transition and the user's desire for those changes. A larger number of customers can be served without any mess due to the advent of innovative technologies compared to the sit and dine model where customers will be lost at peak hours. Thus, the study focuses primarily on customer satisfaction towards delivery format keeps customers loyal and how it manages costs effectively and increases business output (Hassan et al., 2015; Athanassopoulos, 2000).

Review of literature

1. **Kimes (2011)**, in his study, found stated that perceived control and perceived convenience associated with the online food ordering services were important for both users and non-users. Non-users need more personal interaction and also had higher technology anxiety to use the service.
2. **Kimes (2011)**, said that the amount of increase in online food ordering is because of convenience and control. Almost half of the population has ordered food online. Personal interaction with restaurant employees, satisfaction level of the consumer after ordering food online, and changed behavior of the consumers regarding food mobile ordering apps show the perception of consumers for mobile food ordering apps.
3. **Sharma & Saraf (2020)**, the study revealed that e-commerce is rapidly growing worldwide, the food industry is also showing steady growth. In this research paper, they have used the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) as a ground to study the acceptance of online food ordering systems. Their data analysis revealed that the attitude towards online food orders varies according to the ease and usefulness of the online food ordering process and also varies according to their innovativeness against information technology, their trust in e-commerce retailers, and various external influences.
4. **Donkoh et al. (2012)**, stated that the customer's perceptions about food and services are very important for the food and services industry because it helps them to identify the needs and preferences of the customers and satisfy them. In this study, the perception of the customer was judged on various factors.

Objectives of the study

- To find out the demographic profile of the sample respondents.
- To analyse the market trends and customer awareness about online food ordering apps.
- To analyse the factor that influences towards purchasing food.
- To know about the satisfaction level towards the customer.

Research Methodology

The primary data was used in this study through the questionnaire method. The secondary data were collected from various books, journals, magazines, and websites. The sample size has been taken among 100 respondents. The random sampling technique was used in this study.

Statistical tools for analysis

The following statistical tools are used in this study for analysis:

- Simple Percentage Analysis
- Rank Analysis
- Chi-square analysis.

Limitations of the study

- This study is based on the opinion of customers.
- Time constraints in the major limitations of the study.
- This study is restricted to Bengaluru city.

Analysis & Interpretation of Data

Table 1
Demographic profile sample respondents

S.No	Factors	Character	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	53	53
		Female	47	47
		Total	100	100
2	Age	Below 20 years.	39	39
		20-30 years.	15	15
		30-40 years.	40	40
		Above 40 years.	6	6
		Total	100	100
3	Educational qualification	School level	24	24
		Graduate	62	62
		Professional	10	10
		Others	4	4
		Total	100	100
4	Occupation	Business	54	54
		Employees	18	18
		Housewife	9	9
		Others	10	10
		Total	100	100
5	Family monthly income	Below 10000	15	15
		Rs 10001-20000	25	25
		Rs 20001-30000	17	17
		Rs 30001-40000	15	15
		Above 40000	28	28

		Total	100	100
6	Marital status	Married	35	35
		Un Married	65	65
		Total	100	100

Interpretation:

- The above exhibit states that 53% of respondents are male, 47% of respondents are female. 39% of respondents are in the age group of below 20 years, 15% respondents are in the age group of 20-30 years, 40% respondents are in the age group of 30-40 years, 6% respondents are in the age group of above 40 years.
- The above exhibit represents that 24% of respondents are school level, 62% respondents are graduate, 10% respondents are professional, and 4% respondents are others.
- The above exhibit portrays that 15% respondents are below 10000, 25% respondents are Rs. 10001-20000, 17% respondents are Rs. 20001-30000, 15% respondents are Rs 30001-40000 and 28% respondents are above Rs 40000.
- The above exhibit describes that 35% of respondents are married and 65% of respondents are not married.

Table 2
Preferred apps for online food ordering

S.No	Preferred apps	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Zomato	109	72
2	Swiggy	27	18
3	Uber Eats	10	7
4	Food Panda	4	3
	Total	150	100

Interpretation:

The above exhibit indicates that 72% of the respondents prefer Zomato and 7% of the respondent prefers uber eats and 3% of the respondents prefer food panda and 18% of the respondents prefer Swiggy (Alalwan, 2020; Xu & Huang, 2019).

Table 3
Various preferred restaurants

S.No	Preferred restaurants	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Dominos	27	18
2	Meghana Foods	79	53
3	Meat & Eat	14	9
4	Vidyarthi Bhavan	30	20
	Total	150	100

Interpretation:

The above exhibit indicates that 18% of the respondents prefer dominos, 53% of the respondents prefer Meghana Foods, 9% of the respondents prefer Meat & Eat, and 20% of the respondents prefer Vidyarthi Bhavan.

Chi-Square Analysis

The Relationship of Occupation & Satisfaction towards Online Food Ordering Apps Hypothesis

- H0: There is no significant relationship between occupation and satisfaction towards online food ordering apps.
- H1: There is a significant relationship between occupation and satisfaction towards online food ordering apps.

Table 4

Level of Occupation satisfaction

Occupation/ satisfaction level	Level					Total
	Satisfied	Highly satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Highly dissatisfied	
Business	6	3	2	1	0	12
Students	78	28	10	3	1	120
Home Maker	7	2	1	0	0	10
Professional	4	2	0	2	0	8
Total	95	35	13	6	1	150

$$\text{Chi-Square Value } x^2 = \sum (O-E)^2 \div E$$

$$= 0.1924$$

Degree of freedom = (row-1) (column-1)
 = (4-1) (5-1)
 = (3) (4)
 =12

Table Value = 21.03

Interpretation:

In the above analysis, the calculated values (0.1924) are lower than the table value (21.03) at the level of 0.05 significance. Hence there is no significant relationship between occupation and satisfaction towards online food ordering apps (Dirsehan & Cankat, 2021).

Table 5

Rank analysis channel of advertisement for online food ordering apps

Source of Advertisement	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	Total	Rank
Television	59	20	19	14	18	302	5
Facebook	35	39	25	43	8	400	1
YouTube	43	23	58	13	13	380	2
Instagram	46	49	24	21	10	350	3
Others	63	32	20	15	20	347	4

Interpretation:

The above table depicts that the perception and satisfaction towards online food ordering apps that the highest rank towards advertisement through Facebook, Second rank towards YouTube, Third rank towards Instagram, Fourth rank towards others, Last rank towards the television (Agnihotri et al., 2016; Gustafsson, 2009).

Findings of the Study

Percentage analysis

- Majority 53% of the respondents are male
- The majority 40% of the respondents have come under the age group of between 30-40 years.
- The majority 62% of the respondents are graduate
- The majority 54% of the respondents are business
- The majority 28% of the respondents are annual monthly income above Rs 40000 • The majority 65% of the respondents are unmarried
- The majority 72% of the respondents are aware of the purchase through online app Zomato
- The majority 53% of the respondents have purchased food through Meghana Foods restaurant.

Rank analysis

The above table depicts that the perception and satisfaction towards online food ordering apps that the highest rank towards advertisement through Facebook, Second rank towards YouTube, Third rank towards Instagram, Fourth rank towards others, Last rank towards the television.

Chi-Square analysis

In the above analysis, the calculated values (0.1924) are lower than the table value (21.03) at the level of 0.05 significance. Hence there is no significant relationship between occupation and satisfaction towards online food ordering apps.

Suggestions

- Online food ordering services are limited to some areas so they should be expanded.
- The time of delivery must be as soon as possible.
- More restaurants should be added.
- Uneducated can't use apps so ordering by calls should also be taken.
- Service charge should be reduced.

Conclusion

Food delivery apps are now playing a major role in India. The online food ordering system maintains service providing to keep a database and enhance the customer's experience. Most of the customers who order foods through apps are mostly satisfied with the foods they receive. Even the customers who live in the rural area is also satisfied by using the online food ordering apps.

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